

DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE COMPOSITES BASED ON SHAPE MEMORY POLYMER

Qing-Qing Ni, Takeru Ohki, and Masaharu Iwamoto

*Division of Advanced Fibro-science in Graduate School, Kyoto Institute of Technology
Matusgasaki, Sakyo-ku, Kyoto 606-8585, Japan*

SUMMARY: As one of the functional materials, shape memory polymer (SMP) has received much attention from many fields such as industry, medical treatment, welfare and daily life. Based on the large change in modulus of elasticity above and below T_g , the SMP material has excellent shape memory property. In present paper, for the wider applications, the innovative composites based on shape memory polymer were developed. The specimens with different fiber weight fractions, and laminate structures were fabricated respectively, and their mechanical properties were investigated. Then, the influence of fiber weight fraction on the shape memory polymer was evaluated. It was found that mechanical properties of the shape memory polymer based composites heavily depend on both thermal effects and the fiber weight fraction. Furthermore, the damping effect of shape memory polymer around the glass transition temperature was utilized actively in designing the hybrid composites with CFRP laminas, CF cloth and SMP film. The CF cloth was used as the conductive phase for heating. The penetrating impact tests were conducted to investigate the impact characteristics and the damping effects of SMPs when they were embedded in the hybrid composites. It was found that a remarkable improvement was obtained in hybrid composites with SMP films under the supply of electric current.

KEYWORDS: Shape memory polymer, Mechanical property, Energy absorption, SMP composite.

INTRODUCTION

Recently, shape memory materials have received much attention in industries and the other fields, particularly for Shape Memory Alloys (SMAs) that are a group of metallic alloy and exhibit a shape memory effect. On the other hand, shape memory polymers (SMPs) are mentioned as one of such shape memory materials. Although SMPs indicate a phenomenon that the deformed shape returns to the original shape by heating, the mechanism of shape memory effect and the change of mechanical properties in the SMPs were different from those in the SMAs. Compared with SMAs, SMPs have the advantages, such as lightweight, large recovery ability, superior processability and lower cost. Most of SMPs has the glass transition temperature (T_g) around the room temperature. Based on a consequence of the thermo-elastic phase transformation and its reversal at the temperatures above and below T_g , SMPs have excellent shape memory effect. This means that SMPs may also be used as a temperature sensor or an actuator.

In the SMPs, the polyurethane series has following advantages: the forming processes for other thermoplastic polymer can still be used; the shape recovery temperature can be set at any value within $\pm 50K$ around the room temperature; there exist large differences in mechanical properties [1-3], optical property and water vapor permeability at the temperatures above and below T_g . Based on these advantages, the SMP of polyurethane series is expected to have wide applications in the field of industry, medical treatment, welfare and daily life. However, the practical applications for these

materials were quite limited due to low strength of the polyurethane SMP bulk. In this paper, fiber reinforced composites based on SMP were developed in order to overcome the low strength of SMP bulk. Two types of materials, chopped strand glass fiber reinforced SMP and CFRP laminates with SMP films, were developed, and their mechanical property and some particular characterization for practical use were investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. Fabrication of Specimens and Experimental Instruments

For the chopped strand glass fiber reinforced SMP (i.e. SMP/GFRP), the shape memory polymer (DIARY, MM4510) was used as a matrix with T_g at about 318K, and the chopped strand glass fibers with fiber length of 3mm (03MA411J) were used as the reinforcement. The matrix and reinforcements were compounded by a twin-screw extruder at the cylinder temperature of 483K and the screw rotation of 200rpm. The fiber weight fractions were SMP bulk, 10wt%, 20wt% and 30wt%, respectively. Dumbbell type specimens as shown in Fig.1 were fabricated by an inline screw type of injection molding machine after enough drying time for compounded materials at 353K.

Figure 1. Geometric shape and size for SMP/GFRP specimen.

Figure 2. Laminated structure of SMP/CFRP specimen.

Figure 3. Geometric shape and size for SMP/CFRP specimen.

For CFRP laminates with SMP film (i.e., SMP/CFRP), the laminates were fabricated by prepreg sheet (T700S/#2500, fiber volume fraction 58%), carbon fiber cloth (Torayca Cloth CO6151B) with plain texture and SMP films. The carbon fiber cloth was embedded in order to heat the hybrid composites with the supply of electric current. Three types of specimens were shown in Fig.2 with different SMP ratio. Fig.2(a) was made of only CFRP laminates, and Fig.2(b) and (c) were hybrid composites with SMP ratio of 0.25 and 0.50 in thickness, respectively. The geometric shape and size of specimen for a penetrating impact test was shown in Fig.3. In the case of SMP/CFRP composite, CF cloth was kept 5mm length from the edge of specimen for the supply of electric current as shown in Fig.3 (b).

2. Mechanical Tests

For the SMP/GFRP materials, the tensile and thermo-mechanical tests were conducted by using an Instron Universal Testing Instrument (Type 4466) with a temperature-controlled chamber. Heating or cooling for specimens was controlled and the temperature was measured by a thermocouple near the specimen. The tip of the thermocouple was put between two 1.5mm thickness plates with the same material as the specimen to make the same temperature condition within the specimen.

The static tensile test was performed at the cross head speed of 5mm/min within the temperature-controlled chamber at the testing temperatures of 298K(T_g-20K), 318K(T_g) and 338K(T_g+20K), respectively. The strain was calculated by the ratios of the elongation obtained by the crosshead displacement to the span length (60mm) with a maximum of 300% due to the limit of the chamber.

Thermo-mechanical cycle tests were performed to investigate the strain recovery after different number of cyclic loading. Fig.4 shows a schematic of stress-strain curves in a thermo-mechanical cycle. The specimen was loaded to the strain ϵ_m at a constant crosshead speed of 5 mm/min at the temperature T_h (Process 1). Then, it was cooled to the temperature T_l by keeping the same strain ϵ_m (Process 2). After five minutes at the temperature T_l , the load on the specimen was taken off (Process 3), and then the specimen was heated from T_l to T_h during ten minutes under no-loading (Process 4). This is one thermo-mechanical cycle and then the test was repeated to N cycles. The conditions for the thermo-mechanical cycle test were as follows: $\epsilon_m=100\%$, $T_h=338K$, $T_l=298K$, the crosshead speed of 5mm/min, and $N=5$.

Figure 4. The schematic stress-strain curve for thermo-mechanical cycle test.

For the CFRP and hybrid laminated SMP/CFRP, the penetrating impact test was performed. Testing machine used was the oil pressure actuator impact machine (HTM-1, Shimadzu Corporation). In this testing machine, the actuator piston was stroked at a high speed and the punch with load cell on the tip of the piston penetrates the specimen. Then, the impact load and the displacement at the loading point were

measured. The diameter of the punch was 12.7mm and stroke speed of the punch was 1m/s. The relationship between temperature and supply of electric current to CF cloth impregnated with SMP was investigated in order to decide the amount of electric current. The supply of electric current was performed by the grip with zonal thin aluminum for the uniform supply of electric current to CF cloth and the surface temperature on CF cloth was measured by the infrared thermography.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Static Tensile Property

In calculation of the experimental data, the engineering stress and strain were used. Fig.5 shows the stress-strain curves at the testing temperature of 298K(Tg-20K). The figures for 318K(Tg) and 338K(Tg+20K) were omitted. When the temperature was at T=298K(Tg-20K), the 10wt%, 20wt% and 30wt% specimens had small fracture strain, while the bulk specimen was of a upper yielding point and had no fracture within the strain range of 300%. However, the yielding phenomenon was observed for all different fiber weight fraction specimens due to occurrence and growth of local necking during testing. For the stress-strain curves at T=318K(Tg), 20wt% and 30wt% specimens ruptured at the strain of 120% and 220%, respectively. However, the bulk and 10wt% specimens had no fracture within the testing limit strain of 300%. At higher temperature T=338K (Tg+20K), the specimens indicated a lower stress and the final fracture did not occur within the strain range of 300% except the 30wt% specimen. The maximum stresses within the strain range of 300% are shown in Fig.6. The maximum stress increased greatly with the increment of fiber weight fraction at any temperature. This indicates that the fiber weight fraction plays an important role on the maximum stress.

Figure 5. The stress-strain curves in static tensile test at T=298 K for SMP/GFRP.

Figure 6. Maximum stress at different testing temperature for SMP/GFRP.

Figure 7. The Relationship between Temperature and Young's modulus for SMP/GFRP.

Fig.7 shows the relationship between temperature and Young's modulus. The large change of Young's modulus above and below T_g was observed for all of specimens, which is a key point to utilize and control the shape memory effects of SMP based materials. In other words, the result in Fig.7 means that the developed materials may have shape memory effect.

The results in the static tensile tests can be remarked briefly as follows: a obvious increment of the strength of the developed materials when fiber weight fraction increased; a high Young's modulus and high yield stress at low temperature; a large change in Young's modulus above and below T_g for all materials.

2. Thermo-mechanical Cycle Property

Fig.8 shows the stress-strain curves in a thermo-mechanical cycle test. The maximum stresses and Young's modulus in each cycle increased with the increment of the cycle number N . This may be caused by the strain hardening of the materials. Here, let us look at the strain ϵ_r (see Fig.4), i.e., the strain recovered when the materials were heated from T_1 to T_h without loading (Process4).

The relationship between the strain recovery ratio and the number of cycle are shown in Fig.9. The strain recovery ratio is defined by the value of ϵ_r / ϵ_m . In recovery ratio at first cycle, considerable difference appeared for the specimens with different fiber weight fractions. It is clear that the strain ϵ_r in the specimens with fiber weight fractions of 10, 20 and 30 indicated greatly lower value than that in the bulk specimen. But, the strain ϵ_r after second cycle was almost unchanged. However, the parameters, such as the recovery time and temperature, may control strain recovery ratio. The results showed that the amount of reinforcement fibers of 30wt% will be a limit to keep shape recovery effect and the recovery temperature may be a dominant parameter rather than the recovery time in the shape recovery effect.

Figure 8. The stress-strain curves in thermo-mechanical cycle test for 10 wt% specimen of SMP/GFRP.

Figure 9. The strain recovery ratios at 373 K for SMP/GFRPs.

3. Impact Property for Hybrid Composite with SMP Films

For the SMP/CFRP developed for damping components, the penetrating impact test was performed. Fig.10 shows typical load-displacement diagram and penetrating impact characteristics. (P_{max}) is the displacement at the maximum load P_{max} and impact absorption energy was defined as the area enclosed by the load-displacement curve and the line of load $P=0$. The energy E_p was the absorption energy up to the maximum load P_{max} , while the total absorption energy E_T indicated the area with the curve to load zero. The energy absorbed in a penetrating impact test could be classified into the three stages depending on the load-displacement curve. The stage I mainly indicated the behavior up to the occurrence of material failure; the stage II was mainly for crack propagation after material failure and the stage III

indicated the behavior caused by the frictional loss between the specimen and the punch. These three stages and penetrating impact parameters such as P_{max} , E_P and E_T were used to characterize the results in the penetrating impact test.

Figure 10. Typical load-displacement diagram and penetrating impact characteristics.

The load-displacement curves in penetrating impact tests were shown in Fig.11, Fig.11(a), (b) and (c) were the results of the penetrating impact test without the supply of electric current and Fig.11(d) and (e) were those with heated SMP phase under the supply of electric current to CF cloth. In Fig.11(a), (b) and (c), the load-displacement curves were down to zero after the maximum load (P_{max}) was reached and the area in the stage II was hardly observed. CFRP and hybrid composite with SMP phase indicated the similar behavior, because the surface layer for CFRP and hybrid composite with SMP were unidirectional laminar, so that the crack quickly propagates along the angle of fiber orientation. On the other hand, the area in the stage II appeared quite differently with the supply of electric current as shown in Fig.11(d) and (e).

Figure 11. Load-displacement curves in penetrating impact tests for SMP/CFRPs.

Fig.12 shows the maximum load obtained by the load-displacement curves. In the case of impact tests without the supply of electric current, the maximum loads in hybrid composites with SMP phase were higher than that in CFRP because CF cloth was inserted and effectuate uniform reinforcement. The maximum loads in hybrid composites with SMP phase under the supply of electric current were lower than that without the supply of electric current. This maybe was caused by the reduction of the modulus of SMP phase due to the heating under the supply of electric current.

Absorption energy E_p and E_T in penetrating impact tests were shown in Fig.13. The values of both absorbed energies in the hybrid composites were twice as large as that CFRP without the supply of electric current. In the case of the supply of electric current, the areas in stage II and III appeared remarkably and much larger absorbed energy were measured. It is considered that these larger absorbed energy E_p and E_T were caused by the inherent damping effect of SMP under heating and then resulted in large tolerance to deformation. Consequently, these results also suggested a possibility in designing hybrid composites with SMP film to improve impact characteristics with optimum ratio and the heating control of SMP.

Figure 12. Max Load in penetrating impact tests for SMP/CFRPs.

Figure 13. Absorption energy E_p and E_T in penetrating impact tests for SMP/CFRPs.

CONCLUSION

In this study, the GFRP and CFRP composites based on the shape memory polymer were developed and their mechanical property were investigated. The results obtained are remarked as follows.

For the SMP/GFRP materials, the tensile strength of the developed materials became higher with the increment of fiber weight fraction under each temperature condition. It is predicted that there exists an optimum fiber weight fraction between 10wt% and 20wt% to have an extremely low residual strain during cyclic loading. The temperature was a dominant parameter for the shape recovery effect. It was confirmed that developed composites measurably keep the shape memory effect.

For the SMP/CFRP materials, the penetrating impact tests were conducted with and/or without the supply of electric current in order to utilize the damping effect of shape memory polymer. It was confirmed that the impact characteristics of developed materials were improved in comparison with CFRP laminates. By actively control the temperature of SMP phase with the supply of electric current, it was confirmed that the impact absorption energy increased remarkably due to the dumping effect of the shape memory polymer. This suggested that there is a possibility in designing hybrid composites with both SMP films and the heating control to improve impact characteristics.

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